

The Impact of Brand Awareness, and Product Attributes to Increase Purchase Intention (Study Case: Transvision)

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ABSTRACT: In the dynamic landscape of the Indonesian television industry, the rise of over-the-top (OTT) services poses a major challenge to traditional pay-TV providers such as Transvision. Intense competition from emerging OTT providers in Indonesia requires innovative strategies to secure customer acquisition. Indonesia is one of the fastest growing pay-TV markets, with a predicted CAGR of 5% and revenue projections of \$633 million by 2025. The demographic differences between OTT and pay TV users, highlight the need for a customized marketing approach. In detail, Transvision, which offers pay TV services through Android TV box devices, faces hurdles in terms of market penetration and brand recognition. This study aims to propose an effective transvision marketing strategy while considering the complex dynamics of the evolving television landscape in Indonesia. Using a quantitative approach, the research conducted an examination of customers and hypothesis testing, administering surveys to android TV box users in the Jabodetabek area. The data, processed through SEM-PLS, indicated that social media marketing and electronic word of mouth positively impact brand awareness. Furthermore, significant product attributes, including variety of content and additional features, subscription package price, and payment method options, were found to influence purchase intention. The study concludes that both brand awareness and product attributes play pivotal roles in shaping purchase intention.

KEYWORDS: Pay TV, Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM), Social Media Marketing, Brand Awareness, Product Attributes, Purchase Intention.

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of Indonesia's television industry, the rise of over-the-top (OTT) services poses a major challenge for pay TV providers such as Transvision. According to a Global Data report, predicts that the 2025 revenue will be \$633 million, with a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5% from 2020 to 2025 [1]. The robust growth of pay TV in Indonesia can be attributed to a variety of factors. First, the uneven distribution of the Internet within the country affects the adoption of OTT services. Despite Indonesia's large population, limited internet access remains a barrier, with internet speeds (23.12 Mbps) well below the global average (63.15 Mbps) and significantly lower than in neighboring countries. Another factor contributing to the continued popularity of pay TV in Indonesia is its appeal of offering excellent broadcast quality and easily accessible free TV channels. The demographic differences between OTT and pay TV users highlight the need for tailored marketing approaches [2].

Transvision, which offers pay-TV services through Android TV box devices, reveals challenges in market penetration and brand awareness. One of the Transvision website (my.transvision.co.id) been observe and shows that 771 visitors to the 'bayar' page and only 7 visits to the 'verify order' page, suggesting a low conversion of visitors to purchasers and subsequent subscribers. This trend reflects a potential downturn in user purchase activity. Furthermore, a Google Trends analysis indicates that Transvision's brand awareness is comparatively lower than similar competitors. In response to these challenges, it is crucial for Transvision to prioritize efforts in enhancing brand awareness and formulating strategies tailored to the target market.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework [3]

METHODOLOGY

The research adopts a quantitative methodology to investigate the impact of brand awareness and product attributes for Transvision, a leading pay-TV company in Indonesia. A sample of 221 respondents who are lived in the Jabodetabek area is chosen for the questionnaire, which is the primary method of data collection. Also the product observation through website and interviews are includes to gather as primary data. In addition, secondary data is gathered from academic journals, books, online platforms, and social media. The data collected from the questionnaires is analyzed using SEM-PLS which is particularly suitable for structural equation modeling when the data distribution shows skewness, and there is a limitation on the number of participants [4].

Table 1. Questionnaire Measurements [5]

Measures	Code	Variable	Scale
Electronic Word of Mouth (EWOM)	EWM 1	Informasi di media sosial membuat saya lebih yakin untuk memilih Android TV box	Likert Scale
	EWM 2	Informasi di media sosial memudahkan saya dalam memilih produk android tv box	
	EWM 3	Informasi di media sosial mendorong saya untuk memilih Android TV box	
Social Media Marketing	SMM 1	Konten instagram milik Transvision terlihat menarik	Likert Scale
	SMM 2	Informasi yang dibagikan di akun instagram Transvision selalu <i>up to date</i>	
	SMM 3	Akun instagram Transvision memberikan informasi yang saya butuhkan	
	SMM 4	Memungkinkan bagi saya untuk berdiskusi dan bertukar opini di akun instagram Transvision	
Brand Awareness	BA 1	Saya menyadari bahwa terdapat produk Android TV box Transvision Xstream	Likert Scale
	BA 2	Saya mengetahui logo dan produk Transvision Xstream	
	BA 3	Saya dapat mengenali dengan baik Transvision Xstream diantara produk Android TV box lainnya	
Product Attributes	PA 1	Harga paket yang ditawarkan Android TV box adalah hal yang penting bagi saya	Likert Scale
	PA 2	Kestabilan tayangan adalah hal yang penting bagi saya (tidak sering terjadi error)	
	PA 3	Pilihan metode pembayaran yang tersedia adalah hal yang penting bagi saya	
	PA 4	Kemudahan dalam menggunakan Android TV box merupakan hal yang penting bagi saya (<i>user friendly</i>)	
	PA 5	Variasi tontonan dan fitur pendukung yang dimiliki oleh Android TV box adalah hal yang penting bagi saya	

	PA 6	Menurut saya, penting bagi produk Android TV box untuk bisa digunakan dengan mudah dan lancar	
Purchase Intention	PI 1	Besar kemungkinan saya mempertimbangkan untuk membeli paket premium dari Transvision Xstream	Likert Scale
	PI 2	Saya berniat untuk membeli paket premium Transvision Xstream dalam waktu dekat	
	PI 3	Saya memutuskan untuk membeli Android TV box Transvision dan subscribe paket premium berdasarkan pengalaman orang lain	
	PI 4	Besar kemungkinan saya akan mencoba menonton melalui Android TV box Transvision	
	PI 5	Saya akan membeli paket premium Transvision jika ada film/series yang saya sukai tersedia di dalamnya	
	PI 6	Besar kemungkinan saya untuk melakukan pembelian dari akun sosial media yang saya ikuti	

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 2. Demographic Analysis

Characteristics	Result
Gender	50.2% Female; 49.8% Male
Age	24.9% 41-45 years old; 18.1% 36 – 40 years old; 17.2% above 45 years old
Domicile	31.2% Jakarta; 20.4% Tangerang; 16.7% Depok; 15.8% Bekasi
Occupation	48.9% Full-Time Employee; 22.6% Student; 15.4% Part-Time/Freelance
Monthly Income	24% Rp. 15.000.000 – Rp. 20.000.000; 18.1% Above Rp.20.000.000 17.6% Rp. 3.000.000 – Rp. 5.000.000
Monthly Expense	25.3% Rp. 7.000.000 – Rp. 10.000.000; 23.5% Above Rp.10.000.000; 20.8% Rp.3.000.000 – Rp. 5.000.000

A. Construct Reliability

A composite reliability value between 0.60 and 0.70 is considered appropriate for exploratory research. For more advanced stages of the research, values ranging from 0.70 to 0.90 can be considered acceptable [6].

Table 3. Construct Reliability Result

	Composite Reliability
Brand Awareness	0.934
Electronic Word of Mouth	0.935
Product Attributes	0.928
Purchase Intention	0.928
Social Media Marketing	0.932

Based on the table given, the calculations indicate that each construct has a composite reliability rating over 0.80, which indicates that all constructs are **reliable**.

B. Convergent Validity

The average variance extracted (AVE) is the metric employed to assess the convergent validity of a construct. It is calculated by averaging the variance extracted from all items within each construct. A minimum AVE of 0.50 or above is considered acceptable. An AVE of 0.50 or higher shows that the construct contributes to 50% or more of the variance in the elements that constitute the construct.

Table 4. Convergent Validity Result

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Brand Awareness	0.826
Electronic Word of Mouth	0.828
Product Attributes	0.681
Purchase Intention	0.683
Social Media Marketing	0.773

According to the table provided above, the AVE calculation for all constructions is more than 0.5, suggesting that all constructs are deemed valid.

C. R Square

The calculation of R-square utilized the adjusted R-square value due to the presence of multiple independent variables in this study.

Table 5. R Square Calculation (Author, 2024)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Brand Awareness	0.221	0.214
Purchase Intention	0.252	0.246

- R Square (0.214)
The current model, which comprises X1 Electronic Word of Mouth, X2 Social Media Marketing, and Y Brand Awareness, can only account for 21% of the variance in the phenomenon. The remaining 79% is unrepresentable due to the influence of external variables on brand awareness.
- R Square (0.246)
The current model, which comprises X1 Brand Awareness; X2 Product Attributes; and Y Purchase Intention, can only account for 24% of the variance in the phenomenon. The remaining 76% is unrepresentable due to the influence of external variables on brand awareness.

D. Path Coefficient

Below the criteria of the analysis conducted in this research [7] :

- Comparing the T statistics value

1. If the T statistics value is > 1.96 = research hypothesis is accepted
 2. If the T statistics value is < 1.96 = research hypothesis is not accepted
- Comparing the P statistics value
 1. If the P statistics value is < 0.05 = research hypothesis is accepted
 2. If the P statistics value is > 0.05 = research hypothesis is not accepted

Table 6. Path Coefficient Result (SEM-PLS, 2023)

Variable Relation	Organic Sample	T Statistics	P Value
Brand Awareness → Purchase Intention	0.395	6.365	0.000
Electronic Word of Mouth → Brand Awareness	0.285	3.198	0.001
Product Attributes → Purchase Intention	0.224	3.562	0.000
Social Media Marketing → Brand Awareness	0.259	3.420	0.001

E. T Statistics

Table 7. T Statistics Result (SEM-PLS, 2023)

Variable	Indicator	T Statistics
Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM)	EWM 1	56.276
	EWM 2	76.248
	EWM 3	37.974
Social Media Marketing	SMM 1	25.382
	SMM 2	58.235
	SMM 3	57.477
	SMM 4	40.038
Brand Awareness	BA 1	43.431
	BA 2	51.599
	BA 3	66.875
Product Attributes	PA 1	16.339
	PA 2	13.143
	PA 3	15.975
	PA 4	14.631
	PA 5	25.447
	PA 6	12.353
Purchase Intention	PI 1	19.374
	PI 2	43.347
	PI 3	41.534
	PI 4	46.341
	PI 5	19.548
	PI 6	21.200

Based on the calculations presented in the table, it can be inferred that all the T statistics above the Z-Score value of 1.96. This suggests that there is a statistically significant positive influence between the latent variables. It can be inferred from the questionnaire responses that there is agreement among the respondents regarding the impact of variable x on variable y.

The T-statistic value can be utilized in research to determine the major attributes of a product which influence customer purchase intention. From the results, it can be inferred that the product attributes with the greatest impact on purchase intention are **PA5 (Variety of Content and Additional Features), PA1 (Subscription package price), and PA3 (Payment method option)**.

Additionally the significance can be determined by examining the P Value. Based on the previous table calculation, all P values below 0.05 indicate that the relationship between latent variables is accepted, indicating that significantly favorable influence. Then, based on the T statistics and P value analysis, it could be concluded that the H1, H2, H3 and H4 hypothesis are accepted. Following the summary result.

Table 8. Customer Analysis Result (Author, 2024)

Hypothesis	P Value	Conclusion
H1: Electronic Word of Mouth (EWoM) has a positive influence on Brand Awareness	Accepted	Electronic Word of Mouth (EWoM) has a positive influence on Brand Awareness
H2 : Social Media Marketing has a positive influence on Brand Awareness	Accepted	Social Media Marketing has a positive influence on Brand Awareness
H3 : Brand Awareness has a positive influence on Purchase Intention	Accepted	Brand Awareness has a positive influence on Purchase Intention
H4 : Product Attributes has a positive influence on Purchase Intention	Accepted	Product Attributes has a positive influence on Purchase Intention

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research has addressed the challenges faced by Transvision Xstream in the Indonesian pay-TV market to enhance both brand awareness and purchase intention. The study emphasizes the power of electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) and strategic social media marketing as pivotal drivers for improving brand visibility. On the product attribute factor, the study identifies three key factors—diverse content and features, competitive subscription pricing, and flexible payment options—that significantly influence customer purchase intention. However, the study acknowledges the limitation of the proposed models, suggesting the need for further exploration of external variables influencing brand awareness. This underscores the importance of continuous adaptation and consideration of external factors in refining marketing strategies for sustainable subscriber growth in the dynamic pay TV industry.

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